

Problems Related To NAAC Accreditations In Permanently Un- Aided College Of Teacher Education

Dr. Vilas Bhanudas Bandgar

Assistant Professor

Uma Shikshanshastra Mahavidyalya B. Ed. Pandharpur.

Email.vilasbandgar@gmail.com.

Abstract:

The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) was established in the year 1994 with its headquarters in Bangalore. The NAAC is uploading the quality of higher education in India. This paper mainly discuss about the problem related to NAAC accreditation in Permanently Un Aided college of education.

Keywords: NAAC, un-aided, teacher education, higher education etc.

Introduction:

India his one of the largest and diverse education system in the world. Privatization wide spread expansion, increased autonomy and introduction of programmes in new and emerging areas have improved access to higher education. At the same time, it has also led to wide spread concern on the quality and relevance of the higher education (NPE 1986) & the programme of action (POA, 1992) spelt out strategic plans for the policies advocated the establishment of an independent National accreditation agency.

Standardization of Teacher Education Programme is conscientiousness of NCTE & accreditation of institutions is the focus of NAAC. It assures the quality of Teacher Education to fulfill the commitment to quality school education and national development. Therefor, this paper is purposed to reveal the problems and challenges related to NAAC accreditations in the case of P. A. H. Solapur University, Solapur. The problems regarding NAAC accreditations of 7 criterions set by NAAC.

Criteria I Curricular Aspects:

The curricular aspects are the main stay of any educational institution. The curriculum structured as per framework given by NCTE & UGC university through board of studies modify, reconstruction this curriculum to meet their needs & futures requirements. Hence, the teacher educator never any autonomy in curricular design and development.

The curricular aspects, key indicators they are curriculum planning, academic flexibility, curriculum enrichment & feedback system.

- Academic Flexibility: academic flexibility in the schedule & academic plan of the institutions has scope only in the area of implementation of practical and co- curricular aspects which have no value in; final result sheet of the student teachers.
- Feedback on curriculum: from academic peers, students alumni and employers have importance for review design & restructuring the curriculum but they feedback reviews are not communicated to teacher education

Criteria II: Teaching- Learning and Evaluation:

The criteria deals with the efforts of an institution to serve students of different background & abilities through effective teaching learning practices. The key Aspects identified under criterion are admission process & students profile, catering to diverse needs, teaching learning process, teacher quality improvement and evaluation process and reforms best practices in teaching learning and evaluation.

- Teaching learning Process: The emphasis is given on chalk to talk methods and theoretical aspects have more workload than practical field experiences. The technology labs are just museums which are not functional for its true purpose.
- Evaluation process and Reforms: There is lack of particular criteria guidance or tools for internal assessments and practical activities therefore the loss of objectivity is found and facial opinion of the teacher educator's play key role in the regard.
- Admission Process and Student Profile: Admission process for B. Ed. Is centralized for the state and its through specific admission test CET this test assessment of teaching attitude, aptitude, General knowledge and mental abilities.

Nowadays, the demand ratio of B. Ed course is decreasing and issues like miss proportion of students regarding teaching methodology subjects, mal practices in filling the seats due to less demand ratio, unofficial donations or capitation fees for admission etc. Are emerged due to privatization policy .

Criteria III: Research, Consultancy and Extension :

This criterion seeks information on the policies, practices and outcomes of the institution with reference to research, consultancy and extension. It deals with the facilities provided and efforts made by the institutions to promote A research culture and their outcome.

The key aspects identified by NAAC under this criteria are promotion of research, research publication output, Consultancy, extension activities, collaborations and best practices in research consultancy and extension.

- Promotion of Research: Most of the engagement of teacher educators is towards teaching * training activities. The research is not focused them as A vital aspects of the education rather they are attracted towards getting the degree Ph. D.
- Research Publication Output: The research publication outcomes are very little in substance & scholar practices of research & publication are found in rare.
- Extension Activities: The extension activities are implemented as per the guidelines given in the syllabus due to A rushed curriculum & paucity of the time this aspects is ignored by teacher education institutes.
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Criterion IV Infrastructure and learning Resource:

The key aspects identified by NAAC under the creation are the physical infrastructure maintenance of infrastructure library, as learning resource ICT as learning resource other facilities, best practices in infrastructure & learning resource etc.

The purpose of these criteria is to observe and adequacy & optimal use of the facilities available in an institution to maintain the quality of academic & other related activities on the campus. It also requires information on how every constituent of the institution students teacher and staff benefit from them.

Physical Infrastructure and maintenance: The NCTE norms & standards have given clear guidelines this regard but the availability of the physical infrastructure & facilities is on the proper only & most of the institute set aside the infrastructure development by assuming dead investment and un wanted expense. Teacher educators have very little scope for application of modern technology for effective implementation of teacher education programme.

Criterion V: Student Support and Progression:

The role of Teacher education institutions is very insignificant in the placement of potential teachers. Privatization has reduced there curriculum of teachers & this reduced the demand of teacher education courses.

Criterion VI. Governance and Leadership:

The criterion helps of gather data on the policies and practices of an institution in the matter of planning man power requirements, recruitment, training, performance appraisal & finance management bodies are dominant than the principals and teachers. Especially financial authorities of principals are compressed.

Criterion VII. Innovative Practices:

The criterion focus on the specific efforts of an institution that impacted its academic excellence. Any innovative practice is A pathway created to further the interest of the students & the institution. In some extent, granted colleges and few financially strong collages are ready to bring innovations in the field but overall scenarios not satisfactory.

Problems Related to NAAC Accreditation In Permanently Un- Aided College of Education: There are so many problems about the NAAC accreditation in permanently Un- aided college of education but some problems they are follows.

1. There is no such type of physical facilities.
2. Approved principles are not available for so many colleges.
3. There is no any type of grants permanently un-aided college of education.
4. Permanent staff is not available at un-aided college of education.
5. No well commutations between institutions principles and other staff.
6. Library various types of laboratories are not sufficient for such type of colleges.
7. Seven criterions are not fulfilled by them.
8. They don't give the preference for research work.
9. Payment of all staff is not according to present 7th pay scale.
10. Staff members are not satisfied because the following issue.
 - i. Payment are not by government rules.
 - ii. No guarantee of job.
 - iii. Not available for fulfill & qualifying staff.
 - iv. Day by day decreasing of student strength.
 - v. Not availability of service books.

Conclusion:

Due to various concerns of development of teacher education programmes in present phase the permanently un aided teacher training institutes assumes themselves incompetent to meet the main seven criteria are set by NAAC and thus they are not ready to face the NAAC Accreditation. The expected initiatives by NAAC are as.

- i. To provide A mechanism of assistance for growth of institution in the mentioned criterions.
- ii. Organize workshop, seminar etc. Which will orient and motivate the institutes to accreditation and assure them that this will help in improvement of institute.
- iii. To set different scoring schemes for rural, urban, old and new institute which cannot be assessed by same scale.

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